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Executive summary

This deliverable aims at presenting the considerations on business opportunities for the products produced by the technologies being a part of the project to process the collected Marine Litter:

- T6.3 Additivation Process (chemicals, fibers) => High performance composite material in pellets or filaments
- T6.4 Shredding & Press molding => Panels and laminates products
- T6.5 Pyrolysis => Nafta+MGO OR Pyrolysis oil, Carbon Black, Gas

The output products from each technology are described as well as their quality. Considerations in regards of what they can be used for or substitute in the market are described.

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Abbreviations

AC	Acidification
ADe	Resource use, minerals, and metals
ADff	Resource use, fossils
AI	Artificial intelligence
CED	Cumulative Energy Demand
CED-nr	Cumulative Energy Demand - non renewable
CED-r	Cumulative Energy Demand - renewable
EC	European Commission
EF	Eutrophication, freshwater
EM	Eutrophication, marine
ET	Eutrophication, terrestrial
ETX	Ecotoxicity, freshwater
FU	Functional unit
GLO	Global
GW	Climate change
HDPE	High-Density Polyethylene
HTc	Human toxicity, cancer
HTnc	Human toxicity, non-cancer
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LDPE	Low-Density Polyethylene
LU	Land use
ML	Marine litter
Mt	Million tons

OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
PM	Particulate matter
PP	Polypropylene
PV	Photovoltaic system
RER	Europa
RoW	Rest of World
TOC	Total Organic Carbon
WU	Water use

1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex question of the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter (ML) legacy. MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with a full-fledged circular economy and societal-oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort ML; (iii) evaluates over time the performance of ML removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected ML into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions providing also a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) enhances social awareness about the ML issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximise innovation uptake for ML removal within and outside the EU.

2 MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of:

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3 Aim of the Deliverable

The MAELSTROM project aims at testing and evaluating innovative technologies for removing marine litter (ML) in various coastal environments. It seeks to assess the impact of these technologies on ecosystems in selected demonstration sites and to evaluate the economic and societal benefits of the MAELSTROM solutions within local economies.

This deliverable aims at presenting the considerations on business opportunities for the products produced by the technologies being a part of the project to process the collected Marine Litter in the following tasks:

- T6.3 Additivition Process (chemicals, fibers) => High performance composite material in pellets or filaments
- T6.4 Shredding & Press molding => Panels and laminates products
- T6.5 Pyrolysis => Nafta+MGO OR Pyrolysis oil, Carbon Black, Gas

Figure 1 Tasks, technologies, and output products -MAELSTROM agreement.

The aim of the task T6.6 is to assess (i) the final products derived from thermoplastic recycling of marine litter undertaken by TECNALIA in its facilities for possible market prospect and penetration; (ii) preprocessed macro ML collected in Venice, derived by mechanical treatments undertaken by GEES industrial plant (iii) the pyrolysis treatment in MAKEEN facilities;

In the following chapters, the output products from the above listed technologies will be described and assessed.

4 Metallic waste

Written by GEES

4.1 Collected Metal waste

Part of the collected ML was composed of metals, below are some examples:

- Chains used for ballast of the Truck Tires – collected by Robotic Platform (steel)
- Profiles as reinforcing elements of abandoned boats (steel and aluminum)
- Reinforcing elements of pails and small containers – mild steel

Figure 2 Truck tires ballasted with chains

Figure 3 Steel reinforcements of boats 1

4.2 Recycling of collected metal waste

Metal components were processed by PR Ecology, authorized for scrap metal processing.

Here the results – Evidenced in Red

Figure 4 PR Ecology metal waste processing.

PR Ecology treated the metal waste as usual low-grad scrap metal, mixed with other steel scrap metal of usual collection. The tracking of the waste for metal fraction ended at the PR Ecology yard.

Being a low-grad scrap, there were not issues with contaminations.

Figure 5 Ecology scrap metal yard

Here is a picture of the usual scrap metal operation of PR Ecology Srl

4.3 Conclusion – Metal waste

Metal waste collected as Marine Litter can be mixed with land-collected metals and enter the already existing recycling value-chain for low-grad metal. Since the quantity from Marine Litter will be small and no issues were faced as this trial, it is expected that the value of the metal will be similar to land-collected metals.

5 Thermoplastic waste

Written by Tecnia

5.1 Recycling of thermoplastic marine waste

In the Task T6.3 “Thermoplastic recycling of marine litter” corresponding to WP6 Circular economy and sustainability, the marine waste collected in the Venice Lagoon/coast and the Douro River estuary in Porto was analyzed. This collection was carried out within the framework of other WPs. Marine waste was selected choosing materials, thermoplastics polymers, that can be recycled and revalued in a viable way through mechanical recycling to obtain new compounds with improved properties.

Once the properties of the new formulations or compounds obtained were determined, they have been compared with those of commercial products to explore and identify possible business opportunities.

Before comparing the properties achieved with the manufactured formulations with the properties of commercial products, the mechanical recycling treatment applied to marine waste is briefly explained.

5.1.1 Mechanical recycling

The waste received are composed from 3 different elements:

- Buoys (black, yellow) 30Kg
- Fishing rope 30kg
- Plastic beam 10kg

Figure 6 Received marine waste. Left: buoys and fishing rope. Right: plastic beam

The mechanical recycling treatment applied, after cleaning and sorting the marine waste, was the following:

- a) Shredding
- b) Extrusion/compounding
- c) Injection of specimens and testing

a) Shredding process of the waste.

The shredding process aimed to reduce and homogenize the size of the plastic to particles or flakes of approximately 5 mm.

Figure 7 Material after shredding process. a) Black buoys, b) yellow buoys, c) rope on 5mm sieve

b) Extrusion/compounding of the shredded material

The extrusion process is a process in which a plastic is melted to obtain filaments or profiles with constant section in a continuous process. The compounding process is a specific extrusion process in which different chemical products or fillers are fed into the extruder on the molten plastic in a controlled manner by weight. In this way, new plastics can be formulated by making specific mixtures of plastic and additives to meet a specific requirement or to improve the properties of the plastic. Just after the extrusion process, the filament was pelletized to obtain injection pellets.

Figure 8 Left: Extrusion compounding machine from Coperion and Werner used for MAELSTROM with a production rate of 10-60kg/h. Middle: Pellet from black buoy, oxidized buoy and beam. Left: Pellet from yellow buoy

Three different additives available on the market were used, which are specific for the recycling of polyolefins and are described below:

- **Irgacycle PS 030 G from BASF.** Designing for re-stabilization of post-consumer and post-industrial rigid polyolefines (STABILIZER uses in percentages from 0,1 to 5%)
- **SETAcomp LL 01 from SETA Polymers** is LLDPE functionalized with maleic anhydride. It is used as Coupling agent for Polyethylene (COMPATIBILIZER uses in percentages from 1 to 5%)

- **GRAFTBOND SEBS-MAH 02520 CAF from GRAFT Polymer** is a high-performance maleic anhydride grafted SEBS. It is an excellent additive for material toughening, increasing impact strength and flexural properties. (COMPATIBILIZER uses in percentages from 1 to 5%)

c) Injection of specimens

Plastic injection is the process used to obtain most of the plastic objects we use in our daily lives. It starts with plastic in pellet format, which is melted and introduced into a mould. Once the plastic hardens, the part is removed from the mould. In this phase test samples were injected to validate the properties of the material and to be able to analyze its processability and future use. Pellets from original waste parts and pellets of manufactured compounds were injected.

All materials and compounds injected were tested and thermal, physical, and mechanical properties were determined.

Figure 9 Left: Injection machine Arburg All Rounder 2570C. Middle: yellow buoy testing samples. Right: Mix 1 testing samples

The figure below shows a summary diagram of the process and the steps carried out for recycling plastics recovered from the sea.

5.1.2 Comparison between properties of compounds obtained and commercial products.

The following table show the Melt Flow Index (MFI) and Tensile properties of all material injected.

Table 1 MFI and Tensile properties of materials tested.

Manufactured compounds composition	MFI (gr/10min)	Modulus (MPa) E_t	Peak resistance (MPa) σ_m	Peak deformation (MPa) ξ_m	Break Deformation (%) ξ_{th}
Black buoy	1,152	723	22,26	11,40	65,5
Yellow buoy	2,41	440	15,20	12,96	413,8
Beam	0,26	751	25,61	25,61	13,56
Oxidated black buoy	0,86	1021	28,04	10,67	22,3
Oxidated black buoy +0,4% estabilizador Irgacycle	0,951	1031	28,35	10,52	16,9
Beam	0,26	751	25,61	13,56	32,2
Beam +0,4% Irgacycle PS030	0,24	760	24,65	12,36	21,4
Mix (buoys and beam))	0,75	741	24,69	12,98	30,6
Mix+ 0,4%Irgacycle	0,76	705	23,18	13,14	40,7
Mix + 0,4% Irgacycle +4% SEBS (Compatibilizador)	1,218	641	21,61	14,12	44,7
Mix+ Irgacycle 0,5%	0,89	633	22,58	13,79	36,7
Mix+ Irgacycle 0,5% + compatibilizador SETA LLO1 (5%)	0,5	558	22,48	14,92	36,5
Mix+ 20% recycled glass fibre	0,744	1201	26,01	8,64	16,3

Among all the measured properties, the low value of deformation at break of all the tested compounds (framed in red in the table above) stands out. Generally, most polyethylene's, from high-density polyethylene (HDPE) to very low-density polyethylene (LLDPE), have elongation at break values greater than 500%, being able to reach up to 2000. None of the tested materials exceed 70%, and most of them are even below 40%, too brittle.

One way to achieve better results in recycling processes is to combine waste material with virgin material in high percentages, between 30% and 50%. In this way, properties such as elongation would improve considerably. Initially, the manufacture of a compound combining waste material with virgin PE was not considered.

The applications to which these recycled PE's, HDPE, and LDPE are oriented towards the packaging sector, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 11 Sectors and applications to which recycled PEs are directed.

The table below compare estimates of uptake of rHDPE (both pre-consumer and post-consumer material) in different sectors, based on a sector usage split derived from a 2017 Deloitte study 52. This table shows that the largest part of rHDPE is used for construction of pipes.

Table 2 Use of rHDPE compared to European production, key sector applications (sources: PRE, Deloitte, Eurostat)

	rHDPE to Product Application 2018 (Est), Kt	Consumption, 2018, Kt	Implied rHDPE Usage Rate
Packaging	188	3,880	5%
Construction (pipe or sheet)	421	1,533	27%
Other	140	1,672	8%

The next table shows technical data sheets of PEs corresponding to the considered applications.

<p>TECHNICAL DATASHEET</p> <p>POLYETHYLENE TIPELIN 6500E</p> <p>HDPE for non-pressure pipe and sheet</p> <p>PROPERTIES*</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Note</th> <th>Test method</th> <th>Unit</th> <th>Typical value</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>MFR - Melt Mass-Flow Rate (190°C, 2.16 kg)</td> <td>-</td> <td>ISO 1133-1</td> <td>g/10 min</td> <td>0.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Density (23°C)</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 1183-2</td> <td>kg/m³</td> <td>950</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tensile Stress at Yield</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 527-3</td> <td>MPa</td> <td>26</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tensile Strain at Yield</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 527-3</td> <td>%</td> <td>11</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tensile Stress at Break</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 527-3</td> <td>MPa</td> <td>29</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tensile Strain at Break</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 527-3</td> <td>%</td> <td>1450</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Flexural Modulus</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 178</td> <td>MPa</td> <td>1250</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Izod Impact Strength (notched, 23°C)</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 180/A</td> <td>kJ/m²</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Vicat Softening Temperature</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 306/A 120</td> <td>°C</td> <td>126</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ESCR F50 B (10% Igepal CO-630)</td> <td>3</td> <td>ASTM D1693</td> <td>h</td> <td>> 500</td> </tr> <tr> <td>OIT - Oxidation Induction Time (200°C)</td> <td>3</td> <td>EN 728</td> <td>min</td> <td>> 120</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Note	Test method	Unit	Typical value	MFR - Melt Mass-Flow Rate (190°C, 2.16 kg)	-	ISO 1133-1	g/10 min	0.3	Density (23°C)	3	ISO 1183-2	kg/m ³	950	Tensile Stress at Yield	3	ISO 527-3	MPa	26	Tensile Strain at Yield	3	ISO 527-3	%	11	Tensile Stress at Break	3	ISO 527-3	MPa	29	Tensile Strain at Break	3	ISO 527-3	%	1450	Flexural Modulus	3	ISO 178	MPa	1250	Izod Impact Strength (notched, 23°C)	3	ISO 180/A	kJ/m ²	10	Vicat Softening Temperature	3	ISO 306/A 120	°C	126	ESCR F50 B (10% Igepal CO-630)	3	ASTM D1693	h	> 500	OIT - Oxidation Induction Time (200°C)	3	EN 728	min	> 120	<p>TECHNICAL DATASHEET</p> <p>POLYETHYLENE TIPELIN BS 520-14</p> <p>HDPE for Blow moulding</p> <p>PROPERTIES*</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Note</th> <th>Test method</th> <th>Unit</th> <th>Typical value</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>MFR - Melt Mass-Flow Rate (190°C, 2.16 kg)</td> <td>-</td> <td>ISO 1133-1</td> <td>g/10 min</td> <td>0.1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>MFR - Melt Mass-Flow Rate (190°C, 5 kg)</td> <td>-</td> <td>ISO 1133-1</td> <td>g/10 min</td> <td>0.45</td> </tr> <tr> <td>MFR - Melt Mass-Flow Rate (190°C, 21.6 kg)</td> <td>-</td> <td>ISO 1133-1</td> <td>g/10 min</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Density (23°C)</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 1183-2</td> <td>kg/m³</td> <td>952</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tensile Stress at Yield</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 527-3</td> <td>MPa</td> <td>28</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tensile Strain at Yield</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 527-3</td> <td>%</td> <td>12</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tensile Stress at Break</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 527-3</td> <td>MPa</td> <td>34</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tensile Strain at Break</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 527-3</td> <td>%</td> <td>1500</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Flexural Modulus</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 178</td> <td>MPa</td> <td>1400</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Izod Impact Strength (notched, 23°C)</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 180/A</td> <td>kJ/m²</td> <td>24</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hardness - Shore D</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 868</td> <td>-</td> <td>65</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Vicat Softening Temperature</td> <td>3</td> <td>ISO 306/A 120</td> <td>°C</td> <td>130</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ESCR F50 B (100% Igepal CO-630)</td> <td>3</td> <td>ASTM D1693</td> <td>h</td> <td>260</td> </tr> <tr> <td>OIT - Oxidation Induction Time (200°C)</td> <td>-</td> <td>EN 728</td> <td>min</td> <td>40</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Recommended Processing Temperature</td> <td>-</td> <td>-</td> <td>°C</td> <td>180 - 220</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Note	Test method	Unit	Typical value	MFR - Melt Mass-Flow Rate (190°C, 2.16 kg)	-	ISO 1133-1	g/10 min	0.1	MFR - Melt Mass-Flow Rate (190°C, 5 kg)	-	ISO 1133-1	g/10 min	0.45	MFR - Melt Mass-Flow Rate (190°C, 21.6 kg)	-	ISO 1133-1	g/10 min	10	Density (23°C)	3	ISO 1183-2	kg/m ³	952	Tensile Stress at Yield	3	ISO 527-3	MPa	28	Tensile Strain at Yield	3	ISO 527-3	%	12	Tensile Stress at Break	3	ISO 527-3	MPa	34	Tensile Strain at Break	3	ISO 527-3	%	1500	Flexural Modulus	3	ISO 178	MPa	1400	Izod Impact Strength (notched, 23°C)	3	ISO 180/A	kJ/m ²	24	Hardness - Shore D	3	ISO 868	-	65	Vicat Softening Temperature	3	ISO 306/A 120	°C	130	ESCR F50 B (100% Igepal CO-630)	3	ASTM D1693	h	260	OIT - Oxidation Induction Time (200°C)	-	EN 728	min	40	Recommended Processing Temperature	-	-	°C	180 - 220
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Flexural Modulus	3	ISO 178	MPa	1400																																																																																																																																									
Izod Impact Strength (notched, 23°C)	3	ISO 180/A	kJ/m ²	24																																																																																																																																									
Hardness - Shore D	3	ISO 868	-	65																																																																																																																																									
Vicat Softening Temperature	3	ISO 306/A 120	°C	130																																																																																																																																									
ESCR F50 B (100% Igepal CO-630)	3	ASTM D1693	h	260																																																																																																																																									
OIT - Oxidation Induction Time (200°C)	-	EN 728	min	40																																																																																																																																									
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Table 3 Technical data sheets of PEs corresponding to the considered applications.

As can be seen in the technical data sheets, the properties vary depending on the grade of PE considered, HDPE, MDPE or, LDPE. The elongation varies from values around 1500% for HDPE to 500% in the case of LDPE.

By combining the compounds obtained from marine waste with virgin PE, properties within the ranges shown in the technical data sheets could be obtained, so these new compounds could be used in the indicated applications.

5.2 Conclusion - Thermoplastic waste

As indicated in the previous section, by combining the compounds obtained from marine waste with virgin PE, a new recycled material could be obtained with properties suitable for the applications for which this type of material is intended, mainly packaging.

In the mechanical recycling process considered here, there would be some extra costs compared to the processing of virgin material, which would have to do with the collection, classification, separation and cleaning of waste, not with the processing itself, which is similar to that of virgin material. No extra equipment or different conditions would be necessary for the processing of virgin material, so any compound manufacturer could develop compounds based on recycled material in its facilities.

These compounds based on recycled material would have their corresponding "green" label indicating their composition based on recycled material.

6 Recycled Laminates

Written by Gees Recycling.

6.1 Production of recycled laminates – conclusions from D6.4

The planned recycling operations have confirmed the real feasibility of converting a difficult feedstock into useful material and products. The aspects are reported with more information in D6.4. The conclusions for the processing are, that by adopting the right process parameters and with some modifications, Gees Recycling system obtained good results: Even with a so mixed, different and dirty ML waste, it was possible to process it to obtain previsible and repeatable results, and energy and

environmental impacts were not higher compared to recycling of other waste done by Gees, as shown from LCA Analysis (D6.7).

The preparation of the ML for recycling is the only part of process that differs from standard Gees operation, in specific:

- Nets and floaters gave no problems, once processed with the right shredder – single rotor, organic contamination limited
- Big HDPE buoys presented sometimes high organic presence of mussels and required handwork for cleaning
- Boat parts required a more accurate sorting process, mostly for identifying the hidden metal parts inside fiberglass components

Cost increases were limited and may be paid from the collection fees. Processing costs were not different from standard Gees waste feedstock once transformed into granulate. MAELSTROM Sourced in production behave more or less like other waste feedstocks and didn't need a higher percentages of bonding agents or longer curing times.

6.2 Recycled laminates produced from Marine Litter – market considerations

Collected Marine Litter was at the Gees Recycling facility made into recycled laminates. These laminates are compared with other laminates produced at Gees Recycling.

- Project collected materials/feedstock from waste is given a unique alternative by this process since due to a long term decay of exposure in the environment a costly and complex alternative is collection to be sent in landfill.
- Materials and panels produced have constant and repeatable quality comparable with other products made by Gees from other composite waste coming from automotive or building sectors.
- MAELSTROM produced panels maintains the advantages of recycled composites panels: Lower specific weight respect engineered stone and solid surfaces, insensibility to water and liquids, strong screw retention, machineability without special tools.
- System demonstrated the complete tracking from ML location to refined product in the market.

Figure 12 Panels produced from Marine Litter

Panels are available in a standard size of 2500 x 1240 mm and thicknesses ranging from 8 to 30 mm, offered in two versions:

- D'Ecò MAELSTROM XL, of large grain and particles, that still show the original colors of the marine litter – in particular of the abandoned boats
- D'Ecò MAELSTROM S, with a grain and aspect not different of our traditional product

Figure 13 D'ecò MAELSTROM XL

Figure 14 D'Ecò MAELSTROM S

MAELSTROM Panels competitors

Table 4 MAELSTROM Panels competitors

Material	Recycled content	Water resistant	Specific weight	Cost €/m2	Recyclable
Solid Surface (PPMA+ATH)	< 5%	Yes	1,45	>85	NO
HPL Compact	0	Yes	1,55	78	NO
Marine Plywood	0	Medium	0,65	48	Only if not coated/paint
D'Ecò MAELSTROM XL	>94%	High	1,10	56	FULLY

Mechanical properties were found in line with our traditional products

Table 5 Mechanical properties comparison

Flexural properties of the Recycled composite Boards			
Type	Flexural Modulus Mpa	Flexural Strength Mpa	Strain at Break %
Recomplx D'ecò standard	4080	33,3	0,9
D'ecò MAELSTROM XL	4255	36,9	1
d'ecò MAELSTROM S	4035	33,6	0,9

D'Ecò XL – Magnum panels will not feature a standard color card, as their appearance is uniquely determined by the fragments of boats and other marine litter (ML) used in each production batch. This results in an ever-changing, “true life” aesthetic that visually embodies the process and concept behind the product.

The production process is identical for both materials. MAELSTROM S was developed to offer a marine litter-sourced recycled panel with a consistent appearance and the option to select colors, similar to GEES’s standard D'Eco recycling panels.

6.3 Examples of recycled products obtained from ML

Below please find examples of recycled products obtained from Marine Litter and being produced, sold, and distributed by Gees Recycling.

**Benches , solid and too heavy
to be carried away**

Flower container

Flower containers are particularly interesting and attractive in “Green Building” applications :

- Lower weight respect cement and corten steel allow to avoid structural reinforcements
- Cost are highly competitive considering the durability and no maintenance required

- Will not absorb water and liquids, no rot possible, no stains from oxidation like for corten steel

- Standard line of urban-outdoor furniture in production

MAELSTROM

- Synergies with REFRESH project

- Inalterable
- Fully recycled composites
- Cost competitive
- Fully Green Public Procurement compliant

Co-funded by the European Union

- Standard line of urban-outdoor furniture in production

MAELSTROM

- A4 Brochure for Tables
- Benches
- Flowerpots and Planters with Maelstrom scheme on back

Results from EU Research :
From marine litter
100% recycled
100% composite

Urban furniture
Tables & Benches
Planters & Flowerpots
Shock and water resistant
Theft-proof
RFID tracked
Price competitive

Many colors and dimensions available

Gees Recycling Srl - Aviano (Italy) www.geesrecycling.com - geesrecycling@gmail.com

SMART TECHNOLOGY FOR MARINE LITTER SUSTAINABLE REMOVAL AND MANAGEMENT

MAELSTROM identified marine litter sources and accumulation hotspots in Ports (PT) and Vessels (VT) coastal areas.

IDENTIFY
Identification of pollution hotspots (ports, marinas, mariculture, etc.)

REMOVE
Public Works in the Port Area (PT) and Vessels (VT) coastal areas

ASSESS
Evaluation of the efficiency and the long-term effects on ecosystems of the technologies.

ASSEMBLY
An AI-driven sorting robot separated the litter before the advanced recycling processes.

RECYCLE
Examples of recycle products include chemical precursors, polymers and other materials useful for industrial purposes.

Co-funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union

- Standard line of urban-outdoor furniture in production
- A4 Brochure with Maelstrom scheme on back

Figure 16 Examples of recycled products obtained from Marine Litter and being produced, sold, and distributed by Gees Recycling.

Tables for outdoor use are in standard production and competitive with imported virgin products

Table 6 Price indicators

Type of material	Table size	Recycled content	Wholesale price	Maker
Metal	70 x 70	0	96,90 €	Sklum
Alu+Melamine	70 x 70	0	121,00 €	Gastrodomus
MAELSTROM	70 x 70	>90 %	85,00 €	Gees Recycling

Another product is fully recycled ML composite container for equipment. Their advantage to metal sandwich structures is that they are cost competitive, ensure a much longer durability, no rot or corrosion, insensitivity to salt and marine exposure, better vibration and noise insulation.

Figure 17 Recycled composite SHELTER/CONTAINER

6.4 Recycled Laminates - conclusions:

Products made from ML have several attractive factors:

- Strong identity connected with positive actions – sea and environment protection
- Recycled material visible and identifiable at first look
- Cost not far away from commercial virgin material offers
- Good performances confirmed by official test results
- Exceptionally long durability
- May be fully recycled with the same process at end of life

Products produced, however, suffer still from the limitations of being a “totally new” offering, that does not fit in actual Green Public Procurement simply because never seen before; it takes some time to add these new products for official procurements.

The characteristics and performances make them perfect for purchases inside Italy’s CAM (criteri ambientali minimi /minimal environmental characteristics)

7 Pyrolyzed non-recyclable materials

Written by MAKEEN Energy

7.1 Assessment of product from ML pyrolysis

In task 6.5 marine litter (ML) was processed using low-temperature pyrolysis to obtain a naphtha liquid fraction, a marine gas oil (MGO) liquid fraction and black solid. The MGO was hazy and was therefore distilled to yield three liquid fractions: marine gas oil (MGO), naphtha and a residue liquid. A process overview can be seen in the figure below.

The quality of the MGO obtained after distillation was assessed according to the standard ISO 8217-DMA. From this, it was found that the MGO followed all but two of the analyzed requirements, which was the viscosity and the acid number. However, these properties can be modified using different post-treatments. Additionally, the chlorine content of the MGO was analyzed, which was found to be relatively high. As chlorine is not usually a problem in fossil MGO there is no exact limit. However,

chlorine in contact with water is highly corrosive on metallic parts, causing damage to engines. Low levels of chlorine are therefore desired in fuels.

7.2 Requirements to market-ready products from ML

As stated in task 6.6 products made from ML need to fulfil different requirements to be desirable for off-takers. The products should (1.) be competitive in price and quality, (2.) have a non-issue end-of-life process (3.) have a low environmental footprint and (4.) have a homogenous technical performance. To evaluate the ML derived products for market opportunities all the above-mentioned properties must be considered.

7.2.1 Price and quality competitiveness

The quality of the MGO was evaluated in task 6.5, where it was concluded that different post processes was needed for the MGO to fulfil the ISO 8217-DMA standard for MGO. The chlorine content must also be reduced by post- or pre-processing to limit the corrosive damage on metal parts. Due to these observations, the quality of the produced MGO is not competitive with the fossil MGO as it stands. As for the competitiveness of price, the ML based MGO cannot compete with the price of mass-produced fossil based MGO. Beside pyrolysis a second process of distillation was required to produce the MGO, which separated the oil from pyrolysis into three fractions as seen in figure 4.1: MGO, naphtha and residual oil. This step of treatment is time consuming, adds additional expenses, and ends with a lower yield of the desired MGO product due to loss during the process. To compete with the price of fossil based marine fuel the green aspect of ML derived MGO could be utilized, by applying for a traceability tag certificate as mentioned in Task 6.5.

When producing MGO, the by-product, naphtha, can also be considered of economic value. Depending on the chemical composition of the distilled naphtha, whether it is mainly aliphatic or aromatic, the application and price can be determined. Application examples of naphtha are precursors to gasoline and other liquid fuels, solvents for paints, dry-cleaning, cutback asphalts, the rubber industry, and solvents for industrial extraction processes. Further analysis is necessary to evaluate the specific uses of the naphtha.

7.2.2 Non-issue end-of-life process

Considering the end-of-life prospect, MGO is non-issue since the fuel is being combusted. The black solid and residue liquid contrarily might be sold as a product or act as waste streams, that must be taken care of. As for applications the black solid could be used as additive in asphalt, while the residue liquid could be redirected to a refinery.

7.2.3 Low environmental footprint

Determining the environmental footprint of the product can be quite complex. A life-cycle assessment (LCA) has been conducted by Viegand Maagøe (Appendix X) for a possible/future industrial-scale plant on the basis of the results found in task 6.5. From this it was found that the CO₂ impact when pyrolyzing 1 kg dry ML is 0.61 kg CO₂-eq. Electricity is the main contributor to the CO₂ impact as the impacts of the upstream and downstream processes were not part of the gate-to-gate scope. In the LCA-report, it was likewise found that degas condensate influence several of the categories investigated including climate change biogenic, ecotoxicity freshwater (part 1, part 2 and inorganics), eutrophication marine and human toxicity non-cancer and human toxicity non-cancer inorganics. The degas data has been estimated from other experiments performed at MAKEEN Energy as a degasser was not used in the experiment documented in 6.5. However, a degasser will be used in an industrial scale plant.

7.2.4 Homogenous technical performance

When considering the homogeneity of the product's technical performance, this is highly influenced by the input material to the pyrolysis process. To produce a product with homogenous technical performance, the chemical composition of the ML must also be homogenous and be kept constant in a continuous process. If the composition of the input material suddenly changes, the oil produced will have a different chemical composition and might not have the same physical properties. Therefore, the chemical composition of the input material used must thus reflect the chemical composition of the desired product. It is not all plastic types that are suitable for pyrolysis, as it depends on the chemical structure and the elemental composition of the plastic. Gasoline, MGO, and other fossil fuels mainly consists of hydrocarbons, which are molecules made of hydrogen and carbon. Other atoms are also found in fossil fuels such as nitrogen, oxygen and sulphur with the latter being the most abundant of the three, but all of them being present at low concentrations.

There can also be found traces of metals in the fuels (Chang Samuel Hsu & Paul R. Robinson, 2017).

Most plastic are produced from fossil-based chemicals and therefore, some plastics have the elemental composition suitable for uses as fuel when degraded. However, it is not all types of plastics that can be degraded to fuel-like products as some plastics have a high oxygen content, like PET, or have a high content of other atoms like halogens, as chlorine in PVC. In the following table a list of the 6 most abundant plastics can be seen together with the main degradation products when pyrolyzed.

Table 7 Main degradation products of the 6 most abundant plastic types. O is an oxygen atom and the lines indicate a bond between two atoms. At each bending of the line, there is a carbon atom (C) unless otherwise noted.

Plastic type ^a	Degradation pattern ^{b,c}
<p>Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)</p>	<p>No. 1: 4-(vinylloxycarbonyl) benzoic acid No. 2: Benzoic acid</p> <p>No. 3: Ethan-1,2-diyl divinyl diterephthalate</p>
<p>High-density Polyethylene (HDPE)</p>	<p>No. 1: C₃₀</p> <p>No. 2: C₄₀</p> <p>No. 3: Heptene (C₆)</p>
<p>Polyvinyl chloride (PVC)</p>	<p>No. 1: Hydrogen Chloride No. 2: Benzene No. 3: Toluene</p>
<p>Low-density polyethylene (LDPE)</p>	<p>Decene (C₁₀)</p>
<p>Polypropylene (PP)</p>	<p>No. 1: 2,4-dimethyl-1-heptene No. 3: Propylene (C₃)</p> <p>No. 2: 2,4,6,8-tetramethyl-1-undecene (C₁₅)</p>
<p>Polystyrene (PS)</p>	<p>No. 1: Styrene No. 2: 5-hexene-1,3,5-triyltribenzene</p> <p>No. 3: 3-butene-1,3-diyl dibenzene</p>

^a(Plastic Oceans, n.d.) ^b(Shin et al., 2011) ^c(Scheirs & Kaminsky, 2006)

From Table 7 the degradation products of PET are shown to contain a relatively high amount of oxygen atoms compared to the degradation products from HDPE, LDPE and PP, which are mainly hydrocarbon chains with different lengths. This means that the degradation products from HDPE, LDPE and PP resembles the molecules found in fossil fuels. Furthermore, oxygen can be problematic as a higher amount of oxygen reduces the calorific value, and therefore result in a less energy dense product.

PET can also be problematic to process as it can result in hard crystal-like solids in the piping, based on own test results, and thereby make the process inoperable. PET is therefore not suitable for pyrolysis or to produce MGO.

In Table 7 it can also be seen that one of the main degradation products from PVC is hydrochloric acid, which is a corrosive acid. This can cause problems in the engine when the fuel is combusted, as it can corrode the metallic parts. It can also be a problem in the pyrolysis process as the hydrochloric acid can corrode metallic parts of the pyrolysis plant, when processed in too high quantities. PVC is therefore not suited for pyrolysis to produce MGO.

The degradation products of PS are aromatic hydrocarbons, which can also be found in fossil fuels. Therefore, HDPE, LDPE, PP and PS can be pyrolyzed to yield a product, which resembles fossil MGO.

Besides the 6 most abundant plastics represented in Table 1 there are also other polymers used in different industries. These include ABS, PMMA, PC, POM, PTFE, PA and many others. These are not pure hydrocarbons and contain either oxygen, nitrogen or fluorine in different ratios to carbon atoms. Fluorine is highly reactive and is therefore not acceptable in fuels. Nitrogen can form nitrogen oxides when combusted, which is a pollutant and therefore low concentrations of nitrogen are desired (Chang Samuel Hsu & Paul R. Robinson, 2017). These plastics are available worldwide in lower quantities than the 6 main plastics mentioned in Table 1, and they will therefore constitute as a smaller part of the input material. However, if they appear in the process stream, it is still important to investigate the influence of these plastic types as small changes in the input material can influence the product.

7.3 Fuel standards

According to task 6.6, the produced oil was to be analyzed and compared to standards EN 14214 for biodiesel, EN 590 for diesel fuel, EN 15376 for ethanol mixed

fuel or ISO 8217 for MGO. Based on the chemical composition of the input material to the pyrolysis experiment being polymeric material mainly consisting of hydrocarbons, the standards EN 14214 and EN 15376 are not applicable on the produced product. The EN 14214 standard focuses on fatty acid methyl ester (FAME), which is produced from transesterification of triglycerides with methanol. Triglycerides are found in fats from e.g. animals and plants and are therefore biological based. The EN 15376 standard focuses on ethanol and other alcohols as additive to fuels. The input material for the pyrolysis experiment did not contain polymers with structures, that can result in formation of alcohol upon thermal degradation. Therefore, the produced liquid product cannot meet the requirements of the EN 15376 standard.

The standard EN 590 is a standard for diesel fuel for automotives and the specifications are different from that of ISO 8217-DMA for MGO. However, specifications for cetane index, sulphur content, flash point, carbon residue, ash content, water content, lubricity and viscosity are included in both fuel standards. The produced MGO does not fulfil the requirements for viscosity or sulphur content in the EN 590 standard, but the remaining of the listed property specifications are met. This indicates that pyrolyzing ML may yield a product which can either be upgraded for MGO or for diesel fuel for automotives.

7.4 Processing and product perspectives

Since it is only a small part of the total ML that is meant to be processed by low-temperature pyrolysis, the capital expenditures to build a separate plant to process ML does not match the amount of ML available. Therefore, another business case could be to implement the ML as an input stream in an already existing pyrolysis plant processing post-consumer plastic as mentioned in task 6.5. In this way the ML derived product would be a pyrolysis oil rather than MGO.

Since the project was defined, the market has changed and the attention on pyrolysis oil has increased. This means that the selling price of pyrolysis oil today is higher than that of MGO, which has a price of 750 €/ton compared to an expected 1000 €/ton for pyrolysis oil (Ship & Bunker, n.d.). Beside a higher market value, the pyrolysis oil requires less processing and encourages the circular economy prospect. This is due to the possible recycling of the pyrolysis oil to the chemical industry, that might use the oil in the production of platform chemicals suitable for production of new plastic. In this way, the plastic is being chemically recycled into new plastic or platform molecules creating circularity.

Considering the business case of producing pyrolysis oil rather than MGO, the ML would only be introduced in small percentage in a pyrolysis plant. This results in a dilution of the ML and thereby also of the chloride deposited on the ML. Chloride from the ocean water can form hydrochloric acid (HCl), which is highly corrosive to the process equipment, as mentioned earlier and therefore dilution of this component is desired. Based on knowledge from pyrolysis of the chloride containing PVC, ML must only constitute around 5% w/w of the input material. This means that the ML is going to replace PVC or at least be placed in the same material category that must be tightly regulated. When comparing ML and PVC, the chloride content in the process during operation should be easier to control when using ML. This is due to a lower concentration of chloride in ML compared to PVC. Thus, a steady addition of chloride will happen when introducing ML, while a large and sudden increase of chloride would occur when adding PVC.

Returning to the case of a small-scale plant used only for ML to produce MGO and naphtha, it might be possible to adjust the process parameters of the condensers to increase the quality of the oil from pyrolysis. Thereby the postprocessing of distillation to obtain MGO and Naphtha from the produced oil can be minimized or omitted. In this case of having an optimized plant for ML only, there is a possibility of certifying the MGO according to The International Sustainability and Carbon Certification (ISCC). ISCC is an international certification system supporting sustainable, fully traceable, deforestation-free, and climate-friendly supply chains. The ISCC EU certificate issued in Europe more specifically focuses on reducing the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the transport and energy sector. The MGO from ML in MAELSTROM matches the subject of solid waste streams of non-renewable origin to produce recycled carbon fuels. In particular, the low temperature pyrolysis product of MGO fits the market of sustainable marine fuels where the recycled carbon fuel contributes to the climate-neutral economy goal (ISCC System, n.d.). By applying for the ISCC the traceability of the ML would be increased and thereby possibly also increasing the value of the product as discussed in task 6.5. However, if the liquid pyrolysis product is sold as pyrolysis oil to the petrochemical industries the traceability would be of less or no interest. The oil would be added to a mixed process stream where the following traceability would be difficult. Whether the extra work and costs of applying for traceability and sustainability certificates is worth the increased market value is difficult to determine.

7.5 Conclusion - Pyrolysis

The non-recyclable part of the obtained ML received at MAKEEN Energy was processed by low temperature pyrolysis producing an oil assessed according to the ISO 8217-DMA standard for MGO.

When considering future process plant opportunities for ML two cases are relevant. One case is to dedicate a smaller process plant to only process ML and produce MGO and naphtha. The other case is to include ML in an industrial plant used for processing post-consumer plastic and producing pyrolysis oil.

In the case of having a plant only for processing ML, the marketisation of the pyrolysis product depends on several factors including its homogeneous technical performance. This relies on the input material, as the output product quality is defined by this. When producing fuels, plastic types of HDPE, LDPE, PP and PS are suitable due to their chemical structure of long hydrocarbon chains, while PVC and PET are not. As the input material will differ the technical performance and quality will as well.

Based on the performed experiment from task 6.5 the quality of the produced MGO from ML somewhat matched the standard ISO 8217-DMA for MGO. Beside ISO 8217-DMA, the EN 590 for diesel fuel for automotives is the most suitable standard for the given product.

Considering the price, this cannot compete with fossil based MGO as there are too many process steps that increases the price. However, by applying for the ISCC certification the competitiveness might increase.

By implementing the ML in an industrial pyrolysis, the ML is diluted, which would equalize the impact of the differing input stream, and hence increase the homogeneity of the technical performance and the quality of the product. The competitiveness in price would also increase as pyrolysis oil requires less processing and the market price of pyrolysis oil is expected to be higher than that of MGO. This solution encourages the circular economy as new plastic can be made from pyrolysis oil.

8 Conclusion – all technologies for processing Marine Litter in MAELSTROM

Considerations on business opportunities for the products produced by the technologies being a part of the project to process the collected Marine Litter has been described and assessed. The three technologies are (and further details about the technologies and products can be found in respective reports):

- T6.3 Additivition Process (chemicals, fibers) => High performance composite material in pellets or filaments (D6.3)
- T6.4 Shredding & Press molding => Panels and laminates products (D6.4)
- T6.5 Pyrolysis => Nafta+MGO OR Pyrolysis oil, Carbon Black, Gas (D6.5)

8.1 Metal waste (Gees Recycling)

The part of the Marine Litter being metal waste can be recycled as part of the already existing recycling value-chains. No issues with e.g. salt are foreseen as the Marine Litter metal fraction is considered to be a very small portion of the quantity being recycled.

8.2 Additivition Process (Tecnalia)

Combining the compounds obtained from marine waste with virgin PE, a new recycled material could be obtained with properties suitable for the applications for which this type of material is intended, mainly packaging. There would be some extra costs compared to the processing of virgin material, which would have to do with the collection, classification, separation and cleaning of waste, not with the processing itself, which is similar to that of virgin material. No extra equipment or different conditions would be necessary for the processing of virgin material, so any compound manufacturer could develop compounds based on recycled material in its facilities.

These compounds based on recycled material would have their corresponding "green" label indicating their composition based on recycled material.

8.3 Conclusions for recycled laminates (Gees Recycling)

Gees Recycling demonstrated production of laminates, outdoor furniture, flowerpots, containers, etc. It was concluded that products made from ML have several attractive factors:

- Strong identity connected with positive actions – sea and environment protection
- Recycled material visible and identifiable at first look
- Cost not far away from commercial virgin material offers
- Good performances confirmed by official test results
- Exceptionally long durability
- May be fully recycled with the same process at end of life

Products obtained, however, suffer still from the limitations of being a “totally new” offer, that does not fit in actual Green Public Procurement simply because never seen before; it takes some time to add these new products for official procurements. The Italy’s CAM (criteri ambientali minimi /minimal environmental characteristics) is considered to be a relevant possibility for off-take.

8.4 Conclusions for pyrolysis (MAKEEN Energy)

The marketisation of the pyrolysis product depends on several factors including its homogeneous technical performance. This relies on the input material, and as the input material will differ the technical performance and quality will as well.

Based on the performed experiment from task 6.5 the quality of the produced MGO from ML somewhat matched the standard ISO 8217-DMA for MGO. Beside ISO 8217-DMA, the EN 590 for diesel fuel for automotives is the most suitable standard for the given product.

Price wise the MGO cannot compete with fossil based MGO as there are too many process steps that increases the price. However, by applying for the ISCC certification the competitiveness might increase.

By implementing the ML in an industrial pyrolysis, the ML is diluted, which would equalize the impact of the differing input stream, and hence increase the homogeneity of the technical performance and the quality of the product. The competitiveness in price would also increase as pyrolysis oil requires less processing

and the market price of pyrolysis oil is expected to be higher than that of MGO. This solution encourages the circular economy as new plastic can be made from pyrolysis oil.

8.5 Bibliography - Pyrolysis

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